

BERYLLIUM FLUORIDES. PART IV. FLUOBERYLLATO-OXALATES

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Fluoberyllato-oxalates of sodium, potassium, and ammonium have been described. The salts can be prepared starting either from beryllium fluoride, or from beryllium oxalate. The formation and stability of fluoberyllato-oxalate ion have been studied by thermometry, conductometry and cryoscopically.

Beryllium fluoride in the solid state has been shown to be polymorphic and polymeric in nature having modifications isomorphous with silica in quartz and β -cristobalite forms (Warren and Hill, *Z. Krist.*, 1934, 89, 481; Novoselova and Zimanov, "Uchenye Zapiski Moskov. Gosudarst. Univ. im M.V. Lomonosova", 1955, No. 174, p 7). But in aqueous solution, which reacts faintly acidic due to hydrolysis, it exists mainly as a non-electrolyte, $[\text{BeF}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]^0$ (Linnell and Haendler, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1948, 52, 819). Behaving as a Lewis acid it is known to co-ordinate with more fluoride ions, which act as a Lewis base, to yield the well-known tetrafluoberyllates. Beryllium fluoride has also been reported to co-ordinate with ammonia at a low temperature to yield $\text{BeF}_2 \cdot \text{NH}_3$ (Biltz and Rahlfs, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 166, 355). The present author therefore in exploring this electron-acceptor property of beryllium fluoride has been able to isolate the fluoberyllato-oxalates only.

In a similar way, weakly conducting beryllium oxalate, $\text{BeC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, can also be presumed as the monomolecular non-electrolyte, $[(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)\text{Be}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, the third water molecule being connected with oxalate group. Therefore the preparation of fluoberyllato-oxalates, starting from beryllium oxalate, has also been examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Beryllium fluoride was prepared from $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4$ according to Lebeau (*Compt. rend.*, 1898, 126, 1418). In preparing beryllium oxalate, $\text{BeC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Parson's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 28, 555) was followed.

The conductances were measured in a plastic vessel with a Kohlrausch Universal Bridge, Cat. No. 7401, W. G. Pye and Co. Ltd., Cambridge, England. The glass stems of the two platinum electrodes were carefully covered with wax prior to platinising the electrodes. The thermometric titration and the determination of freezing point were done as usual.

Potassium Fluoberyllato-oxalate, $\text{K}_2\text{BeF}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.—On titrating thermometrically (Table I) a beryllium fluoride solution by potassium oxalate solution, temperature was found first to decrease slowly, and then increase sharply from $\text{BeF}_2 : \text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 = 1 : 1$. These results show that the initial fall of temperature during the titration is caused by the reaction leading to compound formation, which is endothermic, and the subsequent rise by the crystallisation of the compound from the solution, which is exothermic. After the titration was over, crystals were found in the Dewar flask. The crystals were filtered by suction, washed, dried in air, and analysed. (Found: K, 33.97; Be, 4.11; F, 16.31; C_2O_4 , 38.11. $\text{K}_2\text{BeF}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires K, 33.82; Be, 3.90; F, 16.44; C_2O_4 38.06%).

TABLE I

0.4404M- BeF_2 taken = 500 c.c. $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ soln. added = 2M.

Pot. oxalate (c.c.)	..	0	1	2	4	6	8	10	12
Beckman reading	..	3.61	3.628	3.66	3.765	3.87	3.906	3.955	1.48
Change in temp.	..	..	-0.018	-0.05	-0.155	-0.26	-0.296	-0.345	+2.475

The above compound can suitably be prepared as follows. To a continuously stirred beryllium fluoride solution (18 c.c.), containing 3.5 g. BeF_2 , potassium oxalate solution (50 c.c., containing

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14.5 g. $K_2C_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$) was added, when immediately crystals appeared. The solution was then cooled with ice to ca. 10° , and filtered by suction. The rhombic crystals were washed successively with ice-cold water and ethanol, and dried in air; yield 15.3 g. The substance was recrystallised from water. [Found (recrystallised sample): Be, 3.98%; C_2O_4 , 38.03%]. The solubility of the compound, $K_2BeF_2(C_2O_4) \cdot H_2O$, at 29.5° was found to be 3.33 g./100 c.c.

The above compound was also prepared from beryllium oxalate in the above manner by adding a potassium fluoride solution (10 c.c., containing 1.4 g. KF) to beryllium oxalate solution (10 c.c., containing 1.8 g. of $BeC_2O_4 \cdot 3H_2O$). As before, immediately crystals separated, and the solution became hot. After cooling the solution to room temperature, the crystals were filtered by suction, washed with ice-cold water, then with ethanol, and dried in air; yield 1.94 g. (Found: Be, 4.06; F, 16.28; C_2O_4 , 38.05%).

Ammonium Fluoberyllato-oxalate, $(NH_4)_2BeF_2(C_2O_4) \cdot H_2O$.—A beryllium fluoride solution (7.5 c.c., containing 1.5 g. BeF_2) was added to an ammonium oxalate solution (70 c.c.), containing 5 g. $(NH_4)_2C_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$, with stirring, when a faint turbidity appeared. The solution was filtered, and the filtrate was allowed to crystallise in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 . After several days crystals of ammonium oxalate that appeared were filtered off, and the filtrate was allowed to crystallise again. After rejecting the second crop, the third crop of crystals (rhombic), which were different from the previous ones, were filtered, washed successively with ice-cold water and ethanol, and dried in air; yield 1.7 g. [Found: N, 14.73; Be, 4.66; F, 19.63; C_2O_4 , 46.43. $(NH_4)_2BeF_2(C_2O_4) \cdot H_2O$ requires N, 14.81; Be, 4.77; F, 20.1; C_2O_4 , 46.56%]. Solubility of the ammonium compound was determined to be 16.42 g. of $(NH_4)_2BeF_2(C_2O_4) \cdot H_2O$ per 100 c.c. water at 23.5° .

Sodium Fluoberyllato-oxalate, $Na_2BeF_2(C_2O_4) \cdot 1.8H_2O$.—The sodium salt was prepared in the same way as the ammonium salt. [Found: Na, 21.81; Be, 4.23; C_2O_4 , 41.23. $Na_2BeF_2(C_2O_4) \cdot 1.8H_2O$ requires Na, 21.56; Be, 4.22; C_2O_4 , 41.24%]. The compound was found to lose water at the room temperature.

Lead, calcium, silver, nickel, copper, and cobalt (II) salts of the present series could not be isolated by metathetical reactions with the potassium fluoberyllato-oxalate since the corresponding metallic oxalates or fluorides precipitated out.

Besides the thermometric titration (*vide supra*), the formation of the complex fluoberyllato-oxalate ion has also been indicated by the increase in solubility of ammonium and sodium oxalates in beryllium fluoride solution (*vide* the preparation of the NH_4 and Na fluoberyllato-oxalates). The complex ion has been studied by measurement of the conductance of fluoberyllato-oxalate solutions at different dilutions, and of freezing point depression of water.

For the conductometric measurements (Table II) solutions of potassium fluoberyllato-oxalate (recrystallised) at different dilutions were prepared in wax-coated tubes. The conductances were measured immediately after preparation of the solutions, and after twelve days; but no difference was found.

TABLE II

Conductance of potassium fluoberyllato-oxalate solns. at diff. dilutions.

ν (dilution)	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048
μ_{ν} (at 31°) (unmediate)	..	228.2	250	265.6	280	291.4	311	335.8
λ_{ν}	114.1	124.9	132.8	139.9	145.7	155.5	167.9	..
λ_{∞}	153.6	155.5	155.8	157.0	158.3	165.0	175.1	..

The λ_{∞} values have been calculated from Walden's formula $\lambda_{\infty} = \lambda_{\nu} (1 + n_1 n_2 \times 0.692 \times \nu^{-1/2})$, where ν = dilution, n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the ions.

A comparison of the above molecular conductances with those of potassium sulphate solutions indicates that the fluoberyllato-oxalate dissociates into a monovalent cation and a divalent anion. The λ_{∞} values suggest a further dissociation of the complex anion, of which the valency has been calculated to be 2.079 (*i.e. ca.2*) applying Walden's formula (*vide supra*) and utilising values at 32 and 64 dilutions, *i.e.* where λ_{∞} values have been found to be almost the same.

TABLE III

Lowering of f. p. of water by $K_2BeF_2(C_2O_4).H_2O$.
 $K_2BeF_2(C_2O_4).H_2O$ taken in 50 c.c. of water = x g.

x. (g.)	F. P. (Beckmann reading)	Lowering of f.p. (d)	M.W. (m)	No. of ions. (n)
0.0	2.155	..	..	..
0.4838	2.423	0.268	67.07	3.446
0.8033	2.563	0.408	73.14	3.160

The measurement of lowering of f. p. of water by potassium fluoberyllato-oxalate (Table III) shows that the compound dissociates into three ions, probably in the following way :

But there is also a secondary dissociation of the complex anion as evidenced by the value of n slightly > 3 , and this result is in accord with that found by conductometric studies (*vide supra*). As the chemical reactions of Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} etc. (*vide supra*), and their pyridine complex cations yield precipitates of the corresponding oxalates from fluoberyllato-oxalates, the complex anion can be presumed to dissociate as follows :

These experiments therefore indicate that fluorine is more strongly bound to beryllium than oxalate.

Attempts have also been made by the present author to isolate analogous fluoberyllato anions containing salicylate, malonate, formate, acetate or chloroacetate groups by mixing beryllium fluoride and the corresponding sodium or potassium salts of the respective acids, but in no case the ions aimed at could be isolated. In the case of salicylate, it was found that on mixing beryllium fluoride and potassium salicylate, salicylic acid precipitated out.

It was found that on adding acetylacetone to beryllium fluoride solution no reaction took place as was evidenced by the existence of two immiscible layers of liquids. When ammonia was added to this mixture, beryllium acetylacetonate crystallised out.

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